

Contributions from UAB-GICI to Remote Sensing Data Compression

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Learned Data Compression

The Research Group

Group on Interactive Coding of Images (GICI)

Department of Information and Communications Engineering (DEIC)

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), Catalonia

- Our areas of interest span all aspects of signal processing and coding for digital communication and data storage systems, especially, compression of remote sensing imagery.
- Founded in 2002.
- 2002: 2 graduate students, 1 postdoc, 2 senior members.
- 2022: 6 undergraduate students, 3 graduate students, 3 master students, 2 PhD students, 3 post-docs, 4 senior members.
- 17 PhD students supervised; 2 PhD students on-going.
- Journal papers: 87; Conferences: 136; Edited books: 11; Book chapters: 3.

Master & PhD students: origin & committees

Research & Technology Transfer Projects

GICI members participating at OBPDC (alphabetical order)

Joan Bartrina

Ian Blanes

Kevin Chow

Miguel Hernandez

Sebastia Mijares

Dion Tzamaris

Our work on compression

- Types of Compression

Mode	Definition	What do we care about ?	
Lossless	$R = I$	Compression Ratio	Computational Complexity
Lossy	$R \neq I$	Compression Ratio	Distortion: Quadratic Error
Near-Lossless	$R \neq I$	Compression Ratio	Distortion: Peak Absolute Error

- Particularly interested in **on-board** data compression for NewSpace.

Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS)

What is CCSDS?

🌐 The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) is a [multi-national forum](#) for the development of communications & data systems standards for spaceflight.

👥 Leading space communications experts from 28 nations collaborate in developing the most well-engineered space communications & data handling [standards](#) in the world.

🎯 The goal to enhance governmental & commercial interoperability & cross-support, while also reducing risk, development time & project costs.

✈️ More than [1000 space missions](#) have chosen to fly with CCSDS-developed [standards](#).

CCSDS Working Group on Data Compression (SLS-DC)

Space Link Services Area (SLS) (6 Areas within CCSDS)

Bands / Type	Lossless	Lossy	Near-Lossless
Mono	CCSDS-121.0, 1997	CCSDS-122.0, 2005	
Multi	CCSDS-123.0, 2012	CCSDS-122.1, 2017	CCSDS-123.0-B-2, 2019

Field Guide to CCSDS Book Colors

BLUE BOOKS

Recommended Standards

Normative and sufficiently detailed (and pre-tested) so they can be used to directly and independently implement interoperable systems (given that options are specified).

ORANGE BOOKS

Experimental

Normative, but may be very new technology that does not **yet** have consensus of enough agencies to standardize.

MAGENTA BOOKS

Recommended Practices

Normative, but at a level that is not directly implementable for interoperability. These are Reference Architectures, APIs, operation of practices, etc.

YELLOW BOOKS

Administrative

CCSDS Procedures, Proceedings, Test reports, etc.

GREEN BOOKS

Informative Documents

Not normative. These may be foundation for Blue/Magenta books, describing their applicability, overall architecture, ops concept, etc.

SILVER BOOKS

Historical

Deprecated and retired documents that are kept available to support existing or legacy implementations. Implication is that other agencies may not cross-support.

RED BOOKS

Draft Standards/Practices

Drafts of future Blue/Magenta books that are in agency review. Use caution with these ... they can change before release.

PINK BOOKS/SHEETS

Draft Revisions For Review

Draft Revisions to Blue or Magenta books that are circulated for agency review. Pink Books are reissues of the full book, Pink Sheets are change pages only.

Our participation in CCSDS standards

Standard	Year	Data	Mode	GICI's participation	Funding
122.0-B-1	2006	Mono	Lossy	Software	–
120.2-G-1	2015	Hyper	Lossless	Writing, Software	CNES
122.0-B-2	2017	Mono	Lossy	Update, Software	CNES
122.1-B-2	2017	Hyper	Lossy	Design, Writing Software	CNES
123.0-B-2	2019	Hyper	Lossless Near-Lossless	Design, Writing Software	CNES, ESA
120.3-G-1	2019	Hyper	Lossy	Writing, Software	CNES
121.0-B-3	2020	Mono	Lossless	Design	CNES
123.0-B-2	2021	Hyper	Lossless Near-Lossless	Update, Writing Software	CNES, ESA
120.1-G-3	2021	Hyper	Lossy	Writing, Software	CNES, ESA
120.0-G-4	2021	Mono	Lossless	Writing	CNES
124.0	2022	Telemetry	Lossless	Design, Writing Software	CNES, ESA
125.0	2023?	SAR	Lossy	Design, Writing Software	CNES

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

Contributions

Extending

- DWT levels extension.
- Scalability L, P, R, and C.
- Lossless and efficient transcoding.
- Multi/hyper/ultraspectral support.

the CCSDS
Recommendation for
Image Data Compression

for Remote Sensing
Scenarios

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

Outline

CCSDS IDC Recommendation

Extending DWT levels

Adding scalability

Multi/hyper/ultraspectral support

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

The Recommendation for Image Data Compression (IDC)

- First Draft, September 2002.
- Blue Book 122.0-B-1, November 2005. (Pen-Shu Yeh)
- Green Book 120.1-G-1, June 2007. (Pen-Shu Yeh)
- June 2007: Created the Multispectral Hyperspectral Data Compression Working Group. (Aaron Kiely)

Only two implementations available

- A C software from University of Nebraska-Lincoln (USA).
- TER: A JAVA implementation from our group.

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

CCSDS IDC Recommendation: Overview

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

IDC Block Building

Segments are encoded separately.

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

Extending DWT levels Frame mode

Landsat Band 3
7400x7400, 8bpp

target bit rate
0.03125bpp (256:1)

IDC
3 DWT levels
Float 9/7 DWT
PSNR: 23.5dB

TER
5 DWT levels
Float 9/7 DWT
PSNR: 28.1dB

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

Extending DWT levels Strip mode

Landsat Band 3
7400x7400, 8bpp

target bit rate
0.03125bpp (256:1)

IDC
3 DWT levels
Float 9/7 DWT
PSNR: 18.1dB

TER
5 DWT levels
Float 9/7 DWT
PSNR: 27.9dB

CCSDS-122.0-B-1 (also known as CCSDS-IDC)

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Hyperspectral images

sensor bitdepth: 8 bits per component

Image Coding
Remote Sensing
Spectral Decorrelation
Divide and Conquer

sensor bitdepth: 16 bits per component

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Spectral decorrelation

Image Coding
Remote Sensing
Spectral Decorrelation
Divide and Conquer

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Usual spectral decorrelators

Wavelets

- Moderate decorrelation
- Low cost

CDF 9/7 for lossy, **CDF 5/3** for lossless (5 levels).

Karhunen-Loève Transform (KLT) and derivates

- Optimal decorrelation
- Very high cost

Image Coding
Remote Sensing
Spectral Decorrelation
Divide and Conquer

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

	Performance (higher is better)	Cost (lower is better)	Scalability (higher is better)	Memory (lower is better)	Implementation (lower is better)
KLT	+++	+++	---	+++	+
Wavelet CDF 9/7	-	---	+	---	---
Wavelet CDF 5/3	-	---	++	---	---

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Regular Multilevel

Idea: Transform cost is $\sim O(n^2)$.
Therefore, smaller transforms have
a substantially lower cost.

16 components, 4 multilevel clusters

44% of the original cost

a) Single-level

- Very fast
- Local decorrelation

b) Regular Multilevel

- Half as fast
- Global decorrelation

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Different approach

Do not try to approximate the KLT;
find minimal divide-and-conquer structure.

⇒ Pairwise Orthogonal Transform (POT)

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

	Performance (higher is better)	Cost (lower is better)	Scalability (higher is better)	Memory (lower is better)	Implementation (lower is better)
KLT	+++	+++	---	+++	+
Regular Multilevel	+++	-	+	+++	+
Static Multilevel	+++	-	+	+++	+
Dynamic Multilevel	++	--	++	+++	+
Pairwise Orthogonal Transform	+	---	+++	---	--
Wavelet CDF 9/7	-	---	+	---	---
Wavelet CDF 5/3	-	---	++	---	---

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Global comparison

Lossy Transforms

- Coding Performance vs. Speed
- Speed vs. Scalability
- Scalability vs. Coding Performance

CCSDS-122.1-B-2

Global comparison

Lossless Transforms

CCSDS 124.0-B-1: Housekeeping telemetry

Vector 1	Temperature	Altitude	Roll	Yaw	Pitch	Charge
Vector 2	Temperature	Altitude	Roll	Yaw	Pitch	Charge
Vector 3	Temperature	Altitude	Roll	Yaw	Pitch	Charge
...						
Vector N	Temperature	Altitude	Roll	Yaw	Pitch	Charge

Housekeeping telemetry

- Monitor spacecraft state
- Critical for most missions
- Some packets are lost
- Data changes slowly

CCSDS 124.0-B-1 Goals

- Robustness to data losses
- High compression ratio
- Low complexity
(prioritize payload)

CCSDS 124.0-B-1: Housekeeping telemetry

Coding approach

- Mask tracks predictable vs unpredictable
- Transmit mask *changes*
- Transmit *unpredictable* bits

Robustness strategies. Send:

- Redundant mask changes
- Full mask
- Uncompressed input

Blue Book : with Agency Review
Green Book : in progress

CCSDS 125.0-B-1: Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)

SAR crop

- *focusing* needed to get image
- no sunlight needed

SAR properties

- Gaussian distribution
 $\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$
- Varying μ and σ
- Independent real/imaginary components
- Very high throughput

CCSDS 125.0-B-1: Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)

CCSDS 125.0-B-1: Recommendation

- In progress
- Very low complexity
- Optimal quantization and entropy coding
- Adaptive to regions with different μ and σ

H2020 Hi-SIDE

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Partners

AIRBUS

TESAT

STAR-Dundee

STAR-Barcelona

JSD
Integrated Systems Development

HELLENIC REPUBLIC
National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens

UAB
Universitat Autònoma
de Barcelona

ERZIA

KONGSBERG

MODUS
Research Organization

UAB-GICI: current research topics

Point Cloud Compression

Motivation:

3D digital representation

Millions of points

Geometry information

Application

Automated driving

Virtual/Augmented reality

Remote sensing:

- Topography
- Measuring of vegetation/canopy structure
- Prediction of forest stand structure

Challenge

Compression of 3D geometry information

Point Cloud Compression

Results: coding performance

Sequence	All frames (Intra coders)				Unspecified number of frames (Intra coders)		First 100 frames	
	FRL	SP	S3D	TMC13	VDNN	MSVDNN	(Intra coder) FRL	(Inter coder) S4D
andrew9	1.00	1.02	1.12	1.13	-	-	1.01	0.95
david9	0.94	0.96	1.05	1.07	-	-	0.94	0.94
phil9	1.02	1.04	1.14	1.17	0.92	-	1.02	1.02
phil10	0.95	-	-	-	0.83	1.02	0.95	-
ricardo9	0.93	0.95	1.03	1.07	0.72	-	0.94	0.90
ricardo10	0.89	-	-	-	0.75	0.95	0.90	-
sarah9	0.95	0.97	1.06	1.07	-	-	0.96	0.92
<i>Average</i>	0.95	0.99	1.08	1.10	0.81	0.99	0.96	0.95
longdress	0.86	0.89	0.95	1.02	-	-	0.86	0.88
loot	0.83	0.86	0.92	0.97	0.64	0.63	0.82	0.84
redandblack	0.94	0.96	1.03	1.09	0.73	0.87	0.93	0.94
soldier	0.88	0.91	0.97	1.04	-	-	0.88	0.65
<i>Average</i>	0.88	0.91	0.97	1.03	0.69	0.75	0.87	0.83
bask/player	0.80	-	-	0.90	-	-	-	-
dancer	0.77	-	-	0.89	-	-	-	-
<i>Average</i>	0.79	-	-	0.90	-	-	-	-
Egyp/mask	18.20	-	-	11.78	-	-	-	-
Shiva	15.11	-	-	9.68	-	-	-	-
<i>Average</i>	16.66	-	-	10.73	-	-	-	-

Point Cloud Compression

Results: encoding time

Sequence	FRL			TMC13	Speedup over TMC13
	Sorting	Encoding	Total		
andrew9	0.005	0.07	0.07	0.10	1.4
david9	0.006	0.08	0.09	0.13	1.4
phil9	0.006	0.08	0.08	0.12	1.5
ricardo9	0.004	0.05	0.06	0.08	1.3
sarah9	0.005	0.06	0.06	0.09	1.5
<i>Average</i>	0.005	0.07	0.07	0.10	1.4
longdress	0.017	0.21	0.22	0.31	1.4
loot	0.016	0.20	0.21	0.29	1.4
redandblack	0.014	0.18	0.20	0.28	1.4
soldier	0.021	0.27	0.29	0.40	1.4
<i>Average</i>	0.017	0.22	0.23	0.32	1.4
basketball	0.061	0.67	0.74	1.05	1.4
dancer	0.054	0.58	0.64	0.92	1.4
<i>Average</i>	0.058	0.63	0.69	0.99	1.4
Egyptianmask	0.009	0.14	0.15	0.48	3.2
Shiva	0.025	0.44	0.47	1.30	2.8
<i>Average</i>	0.017	0.29	0.31	0.89	2.9

Compact Data Structures (CDS)

Motivation:

- Evolved from the 1990s after the work of Guy Jacobson.
- Data is represented in a more compact form instead of being compressed by a compression algorithm.
- Can be loaded in memory for on-board applications.
- Data can be accessed directly without full decompression.
- CDS in our research: k^2 -tree, k^2 -raster, T- k^2 -raster.
- Our experimental results:
 k^2 -raster (up to 52% in compression gains)
 T- k^2 -raster (up to 61% in compression gains)

Compact Data Structures (CDS)

Results:

- Performance gains for different hyperspectral datasets.
- Performance ranking:
 - Heuristic T-k²raster ← *Best*
 - T-k²raster
 - k²raster
 - Gzip ← *Worst*

[1] Chow, Tzamarías, Hernández-Cabrero, Blanes, and Serra-Sagristà, "Performance Improvement on k2-raster Compact Data Structure for Hyperspectral Scenes," IEEE GRSL 2022.

[2] Chow, Tzamarías, Hernández-Cabrero, Blanes, Seco and Serra-Sagristà, "A Compact Data Structure for Hyperspectral Scenes Based on Raster Time Series," IEEE GRSL 2022 (submitted).

Variable-to-Fixed coding (V2F)

Motivation:

Low complexity entropy coding: Huffman coding

- 1 input symbol \rightarrow variable bit length output

a	\rightarrow	0
b	\rightarrow	10
c	\rightarrow	110
d	\rightarrow	1110
n	\rightarrow	1111

- “annabanana” \rightarrow **0 1111 1111 0 10 0 1111 0 1111 0**
- Variable output length
- Bit mangling: if-else in inner loop

Variable-to-Fixed coding (V2F)

Proposal:

Low complexity entropy coding: Variable to Fixed

- variable inputs \rightarrow fixed-length output
- “a **n** na **ba** na **na**” \rightarrow 00 **01** 10 **11** **01** 01
- allows byte-aligned outputs
- no if-else in inner loop
- fast CPU & hardware processing

Variable-to-Fixed coding (V2F)

Results:

Graphical Processing Units (GPU)

Motivation:

Proposed Codec

Method

Graphical Processing Units (GPU)

Results:

Kakadu is the fastest JPEG2000 CPU commercial implementation

Even on low-end GPUs, the new codec shows improvements over Kakadu

It's expected that processing video instead of images can lead to even further performance increases

2018: Results achieved when coding three high-resolution images captured by the GeoEye satellite.

Graphical Processing Units (GPU)

Results:

Throughput comparison - revisit

Exp. Results

2021: Results achieved when coding video.

Astronomical Data Compression

Motivation:

→ Improvement of detectors and telescopes

→ Large Antenna Arrays (CTA, SKA)

→ **FUTURE PROBLEM!**

↓
Data storage and transfer?

↓
Data Compression

•Anais da Academia Brasileira de Ciências, September 2020.

DOI: [10.1590/0001-37652020200861](https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-37652020200861)

Astronomical Data Compression

Results:

Technique	Integer	Float	Radio
HCOMPRESS	2.64	-	-
JPEG2000 Haar	2.80	-	-
JPEG2000 5/3	2.78	-	-
JPEG-LS	2.76	-	-
CCSDS-123	2.76	-	-
HEVC	2.73	-	-
NDZIP	-	1.36	1.81
ZFP	-	1.73	1.43
BZIP2	2.71	2.22	1.43
FAPEC	2.42	1.94	1.79
LZF	1.43	1.61	1.27
LZMA	2.64	2.38	1.73
SPDP	1.35	1.31	1.77
SZIP	2.43	1.66	1.72
ZSTANDARD	2.46	2.09	1.44

[1] Maireles-González, Bartrina-Rapesta, Hernández-Cabronero, and Serra-Sagrà, "Analysis of Lossless Compressors Applied to Integer and Floating-Point Astronomical Data," IEEE Data Compression Conference 2022.

[2] Maireles-González, Bartrina-Rapesta, Hernández-Cabronero, and Serra-Sagrà, "Efficient Lossless Compression Strategies for 16-bit Astronomical Data," IEEE GRSL, 2022 (to be submitted).

Learned image compression

Current state-of-the-art

Competitive with current standards

Neural network codecs are already highly competitive against compression standards on both natural images and remote sensing data

Lines of research

1. Complexity reduction

Reducing the complexity of the encoder part for on-board application

2. Band-by-band compression

Compressing each band independently to enhance the bands needed by the user.

3. Spectral-spatial decorrelation

Exploiting high spectral redundancy to improve overall compression performance

Opportunities

2. Customised optimisation

Optimising compression for customised metrics or AI applications improving performance in ways relevant to the final users

1. Context information for compression

Exploiting redundancies from periodic flyovers and satellite constellations

3. Integration with computer vision

What we have learned

1. UAB-GICI research group
2. Our experience
 - 2.1 Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
 - 2.2 H2020 Hi-SIDE
3. On-going activities
 - 3.1 Point Cloud Compression
 - 3.2 Compact Data Structures (CDS)
 - 3.3 Variable-to-Fixed coding (V2F)
 - 3.4 Graphical Processing Units (GPU)
 - 3.5 Astronomical Data Compression
 - 3.6 Learned Data Compression

Take-home message:

- Data compression is a critical process in all space missions, also for NewSpace, both for on-board and for on-the-ground data sharing. Better design it from the early beginnings.

Further questions: Joan.Serra@uab.cat